
BITCOIN'S INFLUENCE ON THE S&P 500: A BIDIRECTIONAL ANALYSIS INCLUDING THE FINANCIAL AND ENERGY SECTORS

Word Count - 7905

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1 Introduction

Since 2010, Bitcoin has grown from a niche digital currency to a widely traded financial asset with a market capitalization of over \$1.5 trillion, drawing increasing interest from institutional and retail investors. The S&P 500 is one of the most widely tracked equity indices in the world, acting as a benchmark for U.S. stock market performance and a proxy for global investor sentiment. Given its massive market capitalisation and institutional influence, the S&P 500 is a key indicator of traditional equity market behaviour. Bitcoin's emergence as a trillion-dollar asset has raised questions about its relationship with traditional equity markets.

Economists debate whether a relationship between Bitcoin and traditional equities exists. The Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH) states that asset prices should fully reflect all available information, implying that Bitcoin and the S&P 500 should move independently. However, various studies challenge this, showing inefficiencies in Bitcoin's behaviour (Urquhart, 2016; Gil-Alana et al., 2020). Investor Sentiment Theory provides an alternative behavioural explanation, suggesting that irrational sentiment can cause correlated movements between speculative assets like Bitcoin and the S&P 500 (Ahmed et al., 2023). Additionally, Bitcoin's ongoing financialisation through growing institutional adoption further strengthens the possibility of such interactions.

Recent empirical evidence reflects this shift. Studies like Wang et al. (2020) and Bouri et al. (2022) have found growing correlations between Bitcoin and the S&P 500, with Ahmed et al. (2023) finding bidirectional causality between the two. However, literature exploring the relationship between Bitcoin and sectoral equity indices is scarce. Past studies, Bouri et al. (2020, 2023), mainly highlight sectoral heterogeneity and volatility spillovers, without focusing on causal relationships between Bitcoin and sectoral equity returns. Furthermore, most existing research primarily examines the S&P 500's impact on Bitcoin, with limited investigation into the reverse effect. Building on this, the aim of this dissertation is to explore the bidirectional relationship between Bitcoin and the S&P 500 as well as its Financial and Energy sectors. Additionally, this study addresses the limited control frameworks in prior research by incorporating four key macro-financial variables to reduce omitted variable bias, along with two dummy variables to account for structural breaks in the data.

Through econometric analysis, this paper concludes that there is a unidirectional, short run relationship between Bitcoin returns and returns of the S&P 500 as well as its Financial and Energy Sectors, with Bitcoin exerting influence over the S&P 500 and no statistically significant reverse relationship. This suggests that Bitcoin may act as a leading indicator of stock market sentiment, reflecting its growing financialisation and ability to impact traditional equity markets through behavioural spillovers.

The analysis uses daily data from December 2017 to December 2024, capturing Bitcoin's post-financialisation era and growing integration with traditional markets. A time series econometric approach is employed, using vector autoregressions (VAR), Granger causality tests and Impulse Response Functions (IRF) to determine the direction and magnitude of influence. Adding to previous literature, the VAR models incorporate a broader control variable set to improve robustness and reduce the risk of omitted variable bias.

The study addresses the following research questions:

- Do Bitcoin returns influence returns of the overall S&P 500 index, and vice versa?
- Do Bitcoin returns influence returns of the S&P 500's Financial and Energy sectors, and vice versa?

By answering these questions, this paper aims to clarify Bitcoin's evolving role within traditional markets and contribute to findings on sector-specific analysis.

To determine if a relationship exists between Bitcoin and the S&P 500 and its Financial and Energy sectors, this paper has the following structure. Section 2.1 explores the theoretical foundations for Bitcoin's potential interactions with equity markets. Section 2.2 then covers Bitcoin's potential historical role as a hedge, safe haven and diversifier for the S&P 500. In Section 2.3, previous econometric studies are examined, and areas of improvement are identified.

Within the methodology, Section 3.1 outlines the two models used, followed by Section 3.2 explaining the methodology and its relevance. Section 3.3 outlines the control variable specification, and Section 3.4 plots the cumulative log returns of Bitcoin against the S&P 500, to visually show if a relationship exists between the two assets. Section 4 presents the empirical results, with Models I and II analysed in Sections 4.3 and 4.4, followed by an overall evaluation of results in Section 4.5. Section 5 concludes the dissertation, with limitations and suggestions for future research discussed in Section 5.2, followed by final remarks in Section 5.3

2 Literature review

2.1 Theoretical Foundations:

The efficient market hypothesis (EMH) proposes that asset prices fully reflect all available information at any given time. This implies that it is impossible to predict price movements or make abnormal profits from public information, as markets would already have adjusted accordingly (Fama, 1970). In the context of this paper, EMH suggests that Bitcoin and the S&P 500 index would already reflect historical movements in price and therefore should not exhibit any meaningful correlation based on past price behaviour. However, Bitcoin's market behaviour presents several challenges to this theory. Bitcoin is characterized by excessive volatility (Choi and Shin, 2022) and its susceptibility to speculative bubbles as Bitcoin's price often strays from its fundamental value, with nearly half of the observed prices being driven by speculative behaviour rather than intrinsic worth (Cheah and Fry, 2015). This argument is strengthened by Urquhart (2016), who found that Bitcoin markets fail multiple statistical tests of efficiency. Furthermore, Gil-Alana et al. (2020) identified persistent patterns, known as long memory, in Bitcoin prices, suggesting consistent deviations from equilibrium that are inconsistent with EMH. The EMH is also critiqued by Shiller (1981), who demonstrated that stock prices show excessive volatility relative to changes in dividends, suggesting that psychological and behavioural factors cause market mispricing.

This paper therefore argues that the EMH does not hold for Bitcoin and the S&P 500, raising the possibility of a causal relationship between the two assets. To support this, an alternative behavioural explanation is offered by Investor Sentiment Theory to explain the relationship between Bitcoin and the S&P 500. Investor sentiment can be broadly defined as the expectations of future returns or risks that are not fully grounded in fundamentals but instead reflect market mood or bias (Baker and Wurgler, 2007). As per this theory, speculative assets, especially those that are newer and highly volatile are more susceptible to shifts in investor sentiment. During a crypto bull run, investor optimism may spillover to traditional equity markets, driving capital inflows into the S&P 500. Conversely, crypto market uncertainty and fear could undermine investor confidence more broadly, contributing to declines in equity markets. These responses can lead to short-term co-movements between Bitcoin and the S&P 500 due to correlated investor psychology. When considered with the inefficiencies documented above, this provides a behavioural foundation for the relationship between Bitcoin and the S&P 500.

Building on this, Bitcoin is still undergoing financialisation. In the context of Bitcoin, financialisation refers to the process of it becoming increasingly recognised as a mainstream investment asset rather than a decentralised currency (Magazzino, 2025). As a result, Bitcoin is increasingly influenced by market speculation, institutional participation, and its growing integration into traditional financial systems (Shahzad et al., 2020). Choi and Shin (2022) analysed weekly data from 2010 to 2020, finding a strong

upward trend in Bitcoin prices, coinciding with its growing institutional acceptance and market integration. The introduction of Bitcoin futures contracts by the Chicago Mercantile Exchange (CME) and the Chicago Board Options Exchange (CBOE) in 2017 shifted it 'from the margins of the financial world towards the mainstream', adding 'legitimacy to Bitcoin' (Shahzad et al., 2020, p. 213). This effect was compounded by later developments such as MicroStrategy's adoption of Bitcoin as a treasury reserve in 2020 and Blackrock's filing for a Bitcoin ETF in 2023 (MicroStrategy Inc., 2020; Day, 2023). Bouri et al. (2023) also highlights Bitcoin's 'rapid ascension into mainstream finance' and evidence of stronger ties with US stock markets. As Bitcoin becomes increasingly financialised and integrated with traditional markets, it raises important questions regarding its market behaviour.

2.2 Bitcoin's role as a safe-haven, hedge, and diversifier for the S&P 500

This leads to the ongoing discussions around Bitcoin's role in financial markets, and whether it can act as a hedge, safe haven, or diversifier, with important implications for portfolio management.

A hedge is an asset that offsets the risk of adverse price movements in another asset, reducing total portfolio risk. A safe haven on the other hand, is an asset that retains or increases in value during periods of market stress or extreme downturns, providing protection against losses when the stock market declines (Shahzad et al., 2020). As per the EMH, Bitcoin's price should move independently of the S&P 500; however, the existence of systematic negative correlations as required for hedging or safe haven behaviour would challenge this view.

Early studies by Bouri et al. (2017a) and Dyhrberg (2016) explored Bitcoin's hedging and safe haven capabilities. While Dyhrberg (2016) highlighted Bitcoin's role as a partial hedge against both stocks and the US dollar, Bouri et al. (2017a) found Bitcoin to have limited hedging properties but primarily exhibiting safe haven characteristics for Asian stocks. The COVID-19 pandemic period allowed for a significant stress test of Bitcoin's role in the market. Conlon and McGee (2020) concluded that Bitcoin did not act as a safe haven but rather had its price move with the S&P 500 as the crisis developed. Similarly, Kristoufek (2020) found no safe haven behaviour during the pandemic period. Shahzad et al. (2020) compared Bitcoin and gold's role as safe havens and hedges for G7 stock markets, concluding that gold was a much stronger hedge and safe haven for a majority of markets. Bitcoin, however, only acted as a more effective hedge for the Canadian stock index, while offering some diversification benefits rather than safe haven properties. Overall, the evidence suggests that Bitcoin's functionality as a hedge or safe haven is highly inconsistent and sensitive to market conditions. While pre-2018 studies found limited hedging and safe haven roles, evidence from the pandemic portrays a stronger

positive correlation with equity markets, suggesting Bitcoin behaves more like a risky asset.

While Bitcoin's inconsistent behaviour undermines its reliability as a hedge or safe haven, its historically low and unstable correlations with traditional equities raises questions about its role as a diversifier, prompting various literature in this area.

Portfolio diversification refers to combining low or negatively correlated assets to reduce portfolio risk without significantly sacrificing returns. Bouri et al. (2017a) concluded that Bitcoin may primarily serve as a diversifier rather than a hedge or safe haven. Similarly, Klein et al. (2018) states that 'Bitcoin volatility is distinct compared to other asset classes', implying that its price movements are not aligned with traditional assets, offering portfolio diversification opportunities.

These diversification benefits, however, have changed over time. Ahmed et al. (2023) found empirical evidence of a bidirectional causal relationship between cryptocurrency returns and S&P 500 returns. This suggests a growing interdependence of the two markets, also known as mutual coupling, which contradicts the fundamental attribute of Bitcoin acting as a risk-reducing hedge or diversifier. Furthermore, Bitcoin shows heavy tails in its return distribution (Appendix A), implying a higher probability of extreme price movements compared to the S&P 500 (Nzokem and Maposa, 2024). This implies Bitcoin's benefits as a diversifier have diminished as it becomes more financialised and integrated with traditional market systems and the two assets become more correlated.

Investor Sentiment Theory provides further justification for this inconsistent and time-varying relationship. Due to Bitcoin's speculative nature and lack of intrinsic valuation factors, it is particularly susceptible to investor sentiment. Strong sentiment in equity markets may spillover into cryptocurrencies, enforcing coupling between the two assets. Additionally, big movements in Bitcoin could influence sentiment and risk tolerance within equity markets. This suggests that the relationship between Bitcoin and the S&P 500 may not only be driven by structural factors such as financialisation, but also behavioural dynamics. Additionally, more recent literature provides evidence of a growing correlation between the two assets (Bouri et al., 2022). This supports the critique of the EMH outlined in Section 2.1, highlighting the need for deeper analysis of Bitcoin's evolving relationship with traditional markets, not only for whether Bitcoin can protect portfolios but also whether Bitcoin influences or is influenced by broader market movements, thus necessitating a bidirectional examination.

2.3 Econometric Studies

The literature on the relationship between Bitcoin and the S&P 500 uses varying econometric methodologies. Common approaches include Vector Autoregression (VAR) models, Granger Causality tests, and volatility modelling techniques such as GARCH models. Although research on this topic is broad, to best investigate the aim of this paper, studies employing time series analysis using VAR frameworks are most relevant. Additionally, due to limitations in research scope and word count, this review focuses only on studies most aligned in aim and relevance.

Wang et al. (2020) used a structural VAR model and IRF analysis to examine the relationship between Bitcoin and three major stock indices including the S&P 500. The study finds that S&P 500 stock growth has a significantly strong influence on Bitcoin, with no reverse effect of Bitcoin on the S&P 500. However, the model employed in this study solely focuses on the relationship between Bitcoin and stock indices, excluding control variables, thus risking omitted variable bias (Wilms et al., 2021). Therefore, the detected impact of the S&P 500 on Bitcoin might be partially influenced by other external factors such as economic conditions and shifts in market sentiment.

Additional econometric analysis on this topic includes Ahmed et al. (2023) who used VAR, Granger Causality, and cumulative IRFs on daily data from January 2018 to December 2021 to investigate the relationship between the S&P 500 and the five largest cryptocurrencies, naturally including Bitcoin. This study found evidence of bidirectional causality between the returns of the S&P 500 and Bitcoin, however they noted this impact was asymmetric, with S&P 500 returns showing stronger spillover effects on crypto returns. Ahmed et al.'s (2023) use of Brent Oil and 10-year Treasury bill returns as control variables shows improvement from Wang et al. (2020), likely leading to increased robustness of the results and the conclusion of significant bidirectional causality. However, this paper argues that the used control set is still limited with too much of a focus on the oil market and general financial conditions. A more prudent methodology would incorporate a wider range of control variables, encompassing market sentiment, currency dynamics, alternative safe haven asset movements and financial conditions.

In contrast to other studies, Bouri et al. (2020) states that use of broad market indices may mask the characteristics of various sectors, highlighting the importance of granular, sector-specific analysis. The study investigated the role of cryptocurrencies, inclusive of Bitcoin, as a hedge or safe haven for US equity sectors. The findings concluded that the impact of cryptocurrencies on the S&P 500's sectors were 'somewhat heterogeneous', highlighting the need for further sector-specific analysis. However, this study primarily focuses on using cross-quantilograms to assess hedge/safe haven roles, specifically during market stress, rather than modelling the dynamic causal relationship between Bitcoin and the S&P 500. These findings highlight the uneven impact of Bitcoin across various sectors of the economy, suggesting the need for a deeper understanding of how

cryptocurrencies impact specific industries rather than the overall market. This is further reinforced by Bouri et al. (2023) who explicitly emphasises that studies at the sectoral level are few but necessary due to observed sectoral heterogeneity in the Bitcoin-stock market relationship. Building on this gap, this paper examines the relationship between the financial and energy sectors of the S&P 500 alongside the overall index.

This paper selected the financial and energy sectors due to their strong theoretical ties to Bitcoin. There is substantial evidence of Bitcoin's increasing integration into traditional financial markets and evolution as a financial asset. Furthermore, Bitcoin's underlying technologies have been adopted in applications within various FinTech companies (Bouri et al., 2023). This suggests a direct link and likely interdependency between Bitcoin and the financial sector, justifying an analysis of their relationship. Additionally, the process of producing Bitcoin, known as Bitcoin mining, is an extremely energy-intensive process (Bouri et al., 2017b). As energy, in the form of electricity, is an essential input for Bitcoin's production, this paper argues that there is a direct correlation between the S&P 500's energy sector and Bitcoin, necessitating further analysis to understand this dynamic. As the causal relationships between Bitcoin and these sectors is a previously unexplored area, this paper contributes to existing literature, providing new insights into the dynamic relationship between Bitcoin and the US stock market.

Additionally, all relationships in this paper are explored through a bidirectional lens. While Wang et al. (2020) found a significantly stronger, asymmetrical impact of the stock market on Bitcoin, Ahmed et al. (2023) explicitly validated bidirectional causality for several cryptocurrencies including Bitcoin. These studies justify the use of a bidirectional approach to fully capture the dynamics between Bitcoin and the S&P 500.

This paper builds on the methodologies utilised in the reviewed studies, employing VAR models, Granger Causality tests and IRFs to capture short-run dynamic and causal relationships between Bitcoin, the S&P 500 and its studied sectors. Furthermore, this study draws on the strengths of Ahmed et al.'s (2023) use of control variables, employing an even more comprehensive set of controls to ensure increased accuracy and robustness. These include the VIX index, the US Dollar Index (DXY), Gold returns and the 10-Year US Treasury Yield.

3 Methodology

3.1 Outline of Models

Model I:

$$SP500_RET_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_{1i} BTC_RET_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_{2i} SP500_RET_{t-i} + Z_t + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots \dots [1]$$

$$BTC_RET_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_{1i} SP500_RET_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_{2i} BTC_RET_{t-i} + Z_t + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots \dots [2]$$

Model II:

$$SPSector_RET_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_{1i} BTC_RET_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_{2i} SPSector_RET_{t-i} + Z_t + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots [3]$$

$$BTC_RET_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_{1i} SPSector_RET_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_{2i} BTC_RET_{t-i} + Z_t + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots \dots [4]$$

This paper constructs two vector autoregressive (VAR) models, each with two equations that aim to capture the short-run dynamics between the variables. In these equations, p is the optimal lag length selected, α_0 is the intercept, β_{1i} & β_{2i} are lag coefficients and ε_t is the white noise error term. Additionally, both models employ control variables Z_t to reduce omitted variable bias which can undermine result accuracy (Wilms et al. 2021).

This study uses returns rather than price levels following standard econometric practice, as returns are typically stationary while asset prices are not, ensuring model validity and reducing the risk of spurious results (Lee, 2025). BTC_RET is logarithmic returns of Bitcoin's market price, sourced from CoinGecko (2024). $SP500_RET$ is logarithmic returns of the S&P 500's daily closing values and $SPSector_RET$ is logarithmic returns of the daily Financial and Energy S&P sectoral indices. Price data related to the S&P 500 was collected through a Bloomberg Terminal (Complete data source list in Appendix B). For all return variables, this paper uses natural log returns calculated using $\ln\left(\frac{P_t}{P_{t-1}}\right)$, where \ln is the natural log and P_t is the asset price in period t .

Model I explores the bidirectional relationship between Bitcoin and the overall S&P 500. Equation (1) investigates the impact of past Bitcoin returns on S&P 500 returns with equation (2) exploring the inverse, i.e. the impact of past S&P 500 returns on Bitcoin's current returns. Model II follows the same structure, utilising equations (3) and (4) to extend this investigation to the sectoral level, focusing on the Financial and Energy sectors. Each sectoral model is estimated separately for the Financial and Energy indices, with $SPSector_RET_{t-i}$ being the respective sectoral return.

This study constructs a set of hypotheses to guide the econometric analysis, tested using Granger causality tests applied within the VAR framework introduced in Section 3.2. Granger causality is used as it helps identify short-run causal relationships, consistent with the aim of this study. If Granger causality exists, it implies that the lagged coefficients of the explanatory variable are jointly significant ($\exists i \in (1, \dots, p)$ such that $\beta_{1i} \neq 0$). Conversely, if Granger causality does not exist, then the lagged coefficients are jointly equal to zero ($\beta_{1i} = 0$ for all $i = 1, \dots, p$) (Stock and Watson, 2001).

Model I: Bitcoin and the S&P 500

- H_{01} : Bitcoin returns do not Granger-cause S&P 500 returns
- H_{11} : Bitcoin returns Granger-cause S&P 500 returns.

- H_{02} : S&P 500 returns do not Granger-cause Bitcoin returns.
- H_{12} : S&P 500 returns Granger-cause Bitcoin returns.

Model II: Bitcoin and the Studied Sectors

- H_{03} : Bitcoin returns do not Granger-cause Financial sector returns
- H_{13} : Bitcoin returns Granger-cause Financial sector returns.

- H_{04} : Financial sector returns do not Granger-cause Bitcoin returns.
- H_{14} : Financial sector returns Granger-cause Bitcoin returns.

- H_{05} : Bitcoin returns do not Granger-cause Energy sector returns.
- H_{15} : Bitcoin returns Granger-cause Energy sector returns.

- H_{06} : Energy sector returns do not Granger-cause Bitcoin returns.
- H_{16} : Energy sector returns Granger-cause Bitcoin returns.

3.2 Explanation of Method

To investigate this paper's aim and research questions, a time series econometric approach is utilised. Time series analysis is a suitable statistical method as it analyses causality between variables over time, while controlling for dynamic feedback effects (Stock and Watson, 2012).

This paper first tests for stationarity using the Philipps-Perron (PP) and Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) tests. Ensuring stationarity is crucial, as non-stationary variables used in VAR tests can produce spurious regressions. Spurious regressions occur when the variables appear to be correlated due to shared trending behaviour, but no true causality exists, leading to invalid results (Granger and Newbold, 1974).

No transformations are expected for Bitcoin and S&P 500 returns, as this study follows standard practice of using asset returns to ensure stationarity of data. This is supported by methodologies employed in Ahmed et al. (2023) and Bouri et al. (2020). All control variables however are individually tested for stationarity and transformed if found to be non-stationary.

Once stationarity is confirmed for all variables, VAR models are constructed for each variable pair to investigate short-run relationships. To avoid over-fitting from excessive simultaneous variables (Bailey et al., 2015), this paper constructs separate VAR models for each relationship explored (BTC \rightleftharpoons S&P 500, BTC \rightleftharpoons S&P Finance, BTC \rightleftharpoons S&P Energy). For the VAR tests, optimal lag length is found in Section 4.2 using the Schwarz Information Criterion (SIC).

After VAR estimation is complete, the results are checked for stability, ensuring that all eigenvalues are inside the unit circle. If the VAR is stable, Granger Causality is tested using Wald tests to examine whether past Bitcoin returns can predict future stock returns, and vice versa. Through the Granger causality tests, the null hypotheses of no granger causality will be tested at the 1% and 5% significance levels. Furthermore, Impulse Response Functions (IRF) are generated to understand and trace the dynamic effects of a one-standard-deviation shock in Bitcoin returns on S&P 500 returns over time (Stock and Watson, 2012)

3.3 Control Variable Specification

To assign the control variables Z_t , this paper draws on the strengths of previous literature, adding further controls to address previous concerns on the specificity of control variables used by Ahmed et al. (2023). This is essential to mitigate the risk of omitted variable bias, possibly leading to spurious correlations (Wilms et al., 2021).

$$Z_t = VIX + Gold_{RET} + DXY + DGS10 + dCovid + dFTX \dots \dots [5]$$

Equation (5) shows the controls used in this study.

The CBOE Volatility Index (VIX) reflects overall market sentiment and expectations of short-term volatility in the S&P 500, serving as a proxy for market uncertainty. Additionally, as gold is considered a store of value, especially during market turmoil, Gold Returns ($GOLD_{RET}$) are used to account for shifts in safe haven demand, with large fluctuations affecting asset allocation. Both of these control variables were sourced from a Bloomberg Terminal.

Furthermore, Bitcoin is primarily priced and traded against the US dollar, hence this study employs the US Dollar Index (DXY) as an additional control variable. Lastly, this study uses the 10-year Treasury Yield ($DGS10$) to account for expectations of long-term interest rates and inflation expectations. Both of these controls were sourced from the Federal Reserve Economic Data (Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis, 2024). Cumulatively, these controls reduce omitted variable bias and improve the model's explanatory power.

Lastly, dummy variables ($dCOVID$) and ($dFTX$) are added for outliers in early-2020 and November 2022, which were discovered by reviewing the error residuals of Bitcoin and S&P 500 returns. Literature suggests that these structural breaks were caused by the Covid market crash in early 2020 (IMF, 2021) and the FTX collapse in November 2022 (Alsulami, 2025). These dummy variables help reduce serial correlation in the VAR framework, improving the study's robustness.

3.4 Sample period justification.

This paper examines the relationship between Bitcoin and the S&P 500 since its initial financialisation. The CME and CBOE introduced Bitcoin futures contracts in December 2017, signalling Bitcoin’s legitimacy and initial integration into financial markets (Shahzad et al., 2020). The sample therefore ranges from December 2017 to December 2024 to ensure the analysis captures the effects of financialisation. Bouri et al. (2022) support the use of post-2017 data, noting that pre-2018, correlations between Bitcoin and the S&P 500 were extremely weak.

By exploring December 2017–2024, this paper contributes to previous literature that usually concludes before 2022. Each variable in the study is measured daily to maximise the number of observations, and better capture short-run dynamics with approximately 1800 observations.

Figure 3.1: Cumulative log returns over the sample period.

Source(s): (CoinGecko, 2024; Bloomberg Terminal)
Own Calculations

Figure 3.1 shows Bitcoin and S&P 500 cumulative log returns over the sample period. The two variables mainly follow a positively correlated pattern post-2020. Before this period however, there is no obvious correlation, with S&P 500 returns marginally increasing, against heavy, predominantly negative, Bitcoin fluctuations. This could be due to the fact that despite initial financialisation in late 2017, Bitcoin was still not a recognised financial asset until its major rally in 2020 which gained it global attention and further institutional adoption. This interpretation is also supported by analysis of the sectoral indices in Figure 3.2

Figure 3.2: : Bitcoin and the S&P 500's Financial and Energy sector cumulative log returns

Source(s): (CoinGecko, 2024; Bloomberg Terminal)

Own Calculations

Figure 3.2 shows Bitcoin and the S&P 500's Financial and Energy sector cumulative log returns. This correlation resembles that in Figure 3.1. The Financial and Energy sectors are positively correlated with Bitcoin returns from 2020 onwards. From December 2017–2019 the correlation between the variables is not as clear, with the sectoral indices remaining relatively stable and Bitcoin showing negative fluctuations. Again, this is likely due to the insufficient integration and institutional adoption of Bitcoin prior to 2020.

The sample analysis suggests that Bitcoin and the S&P 500 likely share a positively correlated causal relationship as this largely matches the graphical interpretation. The following section conducts a detailed econometric analysis to test this.

4 Empirical Results

Following the method in Section 3.2, this paper now presents the econometric results.

4.1 Stationarity

Stationarity exists when a variable has time-invariant covariance, while exhibiting a constant mean and variance. Ensuring stationarity is crucial, as if a variable is non-stationary, a simple linear regression will lead to spurious and inaccurate results (Granger and Newbold, 1974). This paper employs ADF and PP tests to determine if variables used in the model are stationary or not. If the null hypothesis of a unit root is rejected, we can assume stationarity (Dickey and Fuller, 1979; Phillips and Perron, 1988). To identify the optimal lags for the ADF tests, the Schwarz Information Criterion (SIC) is used. This approach avoids over-fitting, ensuring that residuals are not serially correlated (Ng and Perron, 2003). As the PP test corrects for serial correlation, we do not need to specify a lag length for these tests. Table 4 summarises the ADF and PP results. Stationarity is assumed if the null hypothesis is rejected for both ADF and PP tests at the 1% significance level for additional robustness.

Table 4.1: Stationarity tests

	BTC_RET	SP500_RET	SPFin_RET	SPEnergy_RET	SPVIX	GOLD_RET	DXY	DGS10
<u>At Level</u>								
ADF	-43.763**	-24.138**	-18.967**	-44.354**	-4.864**	-41.975**	-14.025**	-1.518
PP	-43.763**	-49.380**	-48.206**	-44.329**	-5.290**	-41.986**	-42.508**	-3.660**
<u>First Difference</u>								
ADF	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-30.717**
PP	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-116.205**

Source(s): Own Calculations

Notes: **denotes rejection of the null hypothesis of the unit root test at the 1% significance level.

Table 4.1 presents the stationarity tests. As expected, all return variables (*BTC_RET*, *SP500_RET*, *SPFin_RET*, *SPEnergy_RET*) are $I(0)$, and therefore stationary at the 1% significance level. Control variables *SPVIX*, *DXY* and *GOLD_RET* are also stationary at the 1% significance level. Though 10-year yields (*DGS10*) passed the PP test for stationarity, when using the ADF test with optimal lag selection as per SIC, it failed to reject the null hypothesis of unit root at either the 1% or 5% significance level. In its first difference, however, *DGS10* was stationary.

4.2 Lag Length Selection

The Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), Schwarz Information Criterion (SIC), and Hannan-Quinn Criterion (HQIC) were computed for lags 1-5 using the VARSOC command in Stata. Five lags is considered the maximum to avoid overfitting, given the nature of the multivariate analysis and daily data frequency. Where the AIC or HQIC optimal lag differed from the SIC, SIC was prioritised. The SIC imposes a heavier penalty for additional parameters than other criterion like AIC, tending to select more parsimonious models, making it more suitable for structural analysis (Lütkepohl, 2005). **Error! Reference source not found.** shows the reported optimal lags, and the selected lag (in bold) for each model.

Table 4.2: Reported optimal lags and selected lag length.

Model	Controls Included	HQIC Optimal Lag	AIC Optimal Lag	SBIC Optimal Lag	Selected Lag Length
BTC ↔ S&P 500	<i>SPVIX, GOLD_RET</i> <i>DXY, DGS10</i>	4	3	2	2
BTC ↔ S&P Finance Sector	<i>SPVIX, GOLD_RET</i> <i>DXY, DGS10</i>	4	3	2	2
BTC ↔ S&P Energy Sector	<i>SPVIX, GOLD_RET</i> <i>DXY, DGS10</i>	4	3	2	2

Source(s): Own Calculations

4.3 Model 1: BTC and S&P 500

This section constructs and estimates three separate VAR models to analyse the dynamic relationship between Bitcoin and the overall S&P 500 index, as well as its Financial and Energy sectors. Each model employs four control variables, the VIX (*SPVIX*), gold returns (*GOLD_RET*), the US Dollar Index (*DXY*) and the 10-year Treasury yield (*DGS10*). For each model, this paper will first present the baseline VAR estimation, followed by Granger causality and IRF tests.

4.3.1 Vector Auto Regression

The first model explores the relationship between Bitcoin returns and S&P 500 returns with control variables taken into account. As established in Section 4.2, based on the SIC, two lags were specified. To address the research question, this paper focuses on the equations where Bitcoin and the S&P 500 are the dependent variables. **Error! Reference source not found.** summarises the relevant estimated coefficients, standard errors, and p-values for the second lag of each explanatory variable (Full VAR results available in Appendix E1). The significance of each variable is evaluated at the 5% level.

Table 4.3: Vector Autoregression Results: Bitcoin returns and S&P 500 returns

Dependant Variable	Predictor (L2)	Coefficient	Std. Error	z	P> z	Significant
BTC Returns	BTC Returns	0.0344926	0.0246079	1.4	0.161	No
	SP500 Returns	0.0281745	0.0883972	0.32	0.75	No
SP500 Returns	BTC Returns	0.0174645	0.0069237	2.52	0.012	Yes*
	SP500 Returns	0.0797206	0.0248713	3.21	0.001	Yes**

Source(s): Own Calculations

Notes: * denotes significance at 95% confidence level

** denotes significance at 99% confidence level

The VAR results indicate a unidirectional short-run relationship from Bitcoin returns to S&P 500 returns. The coefficient of the second lag of S&P 500 returns is not statistically significant ($p=0.75$), suggesting that short-run movements in the stock market do not have a clear impact on Bitcoin's returns. However, when testing for S&P 500 returns as the dependent variable, coefficients of both its own past values and Bitcoin returns are statistically significant, implying some predictive power of Bitcoin over the stock market.

4.3.2 Granger Causality Analysis

Before conducting Granger causality tests, the VAR model must fulfil stability and residual autocorrelation conditions for valid inference. The stability test confirmed that no eigenvalues were greater than 1 (Appendix C). Additionally, the Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test for residual autocorrelation (Appendix D) showed no serial correlation at two lags, confirming the model is well-fitted.

Granger causality tests were then conducted to assess the short-run predictive relationships between Bitcoin and S&P 500 returns. Table 4.4 depicts the test results for both the BTC and S&P 500 return equations (Full results in Appendix F1).

Table 4.4: Granger causality test for BTC return and S&P 500 Return.

Dependant Variable	Tested Variable	Test Statistic (χ^2)	p-Value	Significant
BTC Returns	SP500 Returns	0.10159	0.75	No
SP500 Returns	BTC Returns	6.3627	0.012	Yes*

Source(s): Own Calculations

Notes: * denotes significance at 95% confidence level

As shown in Table 4.4, Bitcoin returns Granger-cause S&P 500 returns, with the test statistic statistically significant at the 5% level, supporting the VAR findings in Section

4.3.1. However, the inverse relationship is not supported, as S&P 500 returns are not shown to have any significant causal impact on Bitcoin returns ($p = 0.75 > 0.05$). This supports the unidirectional short-run dynamic established between Bitcoin and the overall S&P 500 index through VAR estimation.

4.3.3 Impulse Response Function Interpretation

To determine the dynamic effects of shocks between Bitcoin and S&P 500 returns, impulse response functions (IRFs) were constructed based on the original VAR model.

The IRF results (Appendix G1) show that a shock to Bitcoin returns has a positive impact on S&P 500 returns, peaking on step two and fading by step five. This implies a brief, but statistically significant impact from Bitcoin to traditional markets, potentially driven by Bitcoin's increased financialisation and speculative spillovers. However, as shown in Appendix G2, the inverse relationship does not hold as a shock to S&P 500 returns shows no significant impact on Bitcoin returns over the 10-step period.

4.3.4 Summary of results

Model 1's results are partially consistent with the literature in Section 2.1, providing evidence of a short-run, unidirectional impact from Bitcoin to the S&P 500. The VAR model suggests that a 1% increase in Bitcoin returns is related to a 1.75% increase in S&P 500 returns 2 days later, holding other factors constant. These findings reject the null hypothesis H_{01} , supporting the alternative H_{11} which proposed Bitcoin returns Granger-cause S&P 500 returns. Conversely, the analysis finds insufficient evidence to reject H_{02} , suggesting that S&P 500 returns do not Granger-cause Bitcoin returns. This is supported by the Granger causality test and IRFs, confirming Bitcoin's predictive power over the S&P 500 at the 5% significance level, implying an asymmetrical causal structure between the two assets.

4.4 Model 2: BTC and S&P Sectoral Indices

This section examines the short-run relationship between Bitcoin returns and S&P 500's sectoral returns. This paper focuses on the financial and energy sectors due to their theoretical integration with cryptocurrencies. The analysis found the dynamics across the two sectors to be quite similar, and to avoid redundancy, this section presents a combined analysis while highlighting sector-specific distinctions when necessary.

4.4.1 Vector Auto Regression

The second model explores the relationship between Bitcoin returns and S&P 500 Financial and Energy sector returns, with controls taken into account. To avoid overfitting, separate VAR models were constructed to assess Bitcoin's relationship with each sector. Based on the SIC, two lags were specified, focusing on equations where Bitcoin or the sectoral indices are the dependent variable. Table 4.5 summarises the estimated

coefficients, standard errors, and p-values for the second lag of each explanatory variable (Full VAR results in Appendices E2 and E3).

Table 4.5: Vector Autoregression Results: BTC returns and S&P 500 sectoral returns

	Dependant Variable	Predictor (L2)	Coefficient	Std. Error	z	P> z	Significant
<u>Financial Sector</u>	BTC Returns	BTC Returns	0.0345759	0.0243769	1.42	0.156	No
		SPFin Returns	0.0251254	0.0705709	0.36	0.722	No
	SPFin Returns	BTC Returns	0.0230268	0.0084311	2.73	0.006	Yes**
		SPFin Returns	0.1056606	0.0244081	4.33	0.000	Yes**
<u>Energy Sector</u>	BTC Returns	BTC Returns	0.0355833	0.0240317	1.48	0.139	No
		SPEnergy Returns	0.0131639	0.0511100	0.26	0.797	No
	SPEnergy Returns	BTC Returns	0.0377281	0.0112781	3.35	0.001	Yes**
		SPEnergy Returns	0.0488885	0.0239861	2.04	0.042	Yes*

Source(s): Own Calculations

Notes: * denotes significance at 95% confidence level

** denotes significance at 99% confidence level

The VAR results indicate a unidirectional short-run relationship from Bitcoin returns to both the S&P 500's Financial and Energy sectors. As seen in Table 4.5, when Bitcoin is the dependent variable, neither of the sector's return coefficients are statistically significant ($p = 0.722$ & $0.797 > 0.05$). This suggests that short-run movements in the financial and energy sectors of the S&P 500 do not significantly impact Bitcoin's returns. However, when testing for the sectoral returns as the dependent variables, lagged Bitcoin return coefficients are statistically significant, at the 1% level for both financial and energy sector returns. Additionally, both sectoral returns are impacted by their own past values, at the 1% significance level for the financial sector and the 5% level for the energy sector. These results imply some predictive power of Bitcoin over both sectors, possibly reflecting increased financialisation and investor sentiment spillovers.

4.4.2 Granger Causality

The stability of both VAR models was confirmed with no eigenvalues greater than 1 (Appendix B). Additionally, the Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test for residual autocorrelation (Appendix C) displayed no serial correlation at two lags, indicating both models were well fitted.

Granger causality tests were then conducted to assess the short-run predictive relationships between Bitcoin and the S&P 500 sectors. Table 4.6 shows BTC return results for SPFin and SPEnergy return equations (full results in Appendices F2 and F3).

Table 4.6: Granger causality test for BTC return and S&P 500 sectoral returns

	Dependant Variable	Tested Variable	Test Statistic (χ^2)	p-Value	Significant
<u>Financial Sector</u>	BTC Returns	SPFin Returns	0.12676	0.722	No
	SPFin Returns	BTC Returns	7.4593	0.006	Yes**
<u>Energy Sector</u>	BTC Returns	SPEnergy Returns	0.06634	0.797	No
	SPEnergy Returns	BTC Returns	11.191	0.001	Yes**

Source(s): Own Calculations

Notes: ** denotes significance at 99% confidence level

The Granger causality results support the VAR findings. As shown in Table 4.6, Bitcoin returns Granger-cause S&P 500 Financial and Energy returns with both coefficients statistically significant at the 1% level. On the other hand, the inverse relationship is not supported as S&P 500 sector returns are not shown to have any significant causal impact on Bitcoin returns at the 1% or 5% significance level ($p = 0.722$ & $0.797 > 0.05$). This supports the unidirectional short-run dynamic established between Bitcoin and the S&P 500's energy and financial sectors.

4.4.3 Impulse Response Function Interpretation

As shown in figures from Appendix G3 and G4, a positive shock to Bitcoin returns lead to a statistically significant rise in both Financial and Energy sector returns. This effect peaks at step two and fades by step five, with the energy sector's returns being positively impacted with a higher magnitude. This implies a brief, but statistically significant impact from Bitcoin to traditional equity sectoral indices, with the energy sector being slightly more sensitive to speculative dynamics or macroeconomic signals reflected in Bitcoin's price movements. In contrast, the figures in Appendices G5 and G6 show that a shock to either the Financial or Energy sectors has no significant impact on Bitcoin's returns.

4.4.4 Summary of results

Model II confirms a short-run, unidirectional impact from Bitcoin returns to the S&P 500 index, including the Financial and Energy sectors. The VAR model suggests that a 1% increase in Bitcoin returns is related to a 2.3% increase in financial sector returns, and 3.8% increase in energy sector returns, both at the second lag and statistically significant at the 1% level. Conversely, the sectoral returns do not significantly impact Bitcoin returns, implying an asymmetric causal relationship. These findings reject the null hypotheses H_{03} and H_{05} , supporting H_{13} and H_{15} , which proposed that Bitcoin returns

Granger-cause returns in the Financial and Energy sectors. The null hypotheses H_{04} and H_{06} cannot be rejected due to insufficient evidence, indicating that neither sector exerts a causal influence on Bitcoin returns. These results suggest that Bitcoin may have stronger spillover effects to sectors that are susceptible to movements in crypto markets, such as financials and energy and are supported by the Granger causality tests and IRFs, confirming short-run predictive effects from Bitcoin to the studied sectors.

4.5 Evaluation of Results

The results of both models are partially consistent with the economic and empirical literature in Section 2, showing a short-run, unidirectional impact from Bitcoin to the S&P 500 and its Financial and Energy sectors. The results support the alternative hypotheses H_{11} , H_{12} & H_{13} , while failing to reject H_{02} , H_{04} & H_{06} due to insufficient evidence, suggesting causality runs primarily from Bitcoin to the S&P 500 rather than the reverse. This reinforces the growing consensus that Bitcoin has become increasingly financialised, evolving from an obscure digital currency to an asset capable of influencing equity markets.

From a behavioural perspective, Investor Sentiment Theory can explain these findings. Sentiment like optimism during bullish runs, or fear during market uncertainty can spillover from Bitcoin to equity markets, especially in sectors with greater exposure and ties to Bitcoin such as finance and energy. The greater magnitude of results observed in these sectors suggests that they are more sensitive to Bitcoin's movements. As outlined in Section 2.3, the financial sector is closely linked to blockchain innovation and crypto-financing trends, whereas the energy sector is directly impacted by the energy intensive nature of Bitcoin mining. These structural links likely increase the studied sector's sensitivity to shifts in Bitcoin performance, making them more vulnerable to sentiment-driven spillover effects.

The lack of a statistically significant impact of the S&P 500 or the studied sectors on Bitcoin is surprising considering the theoretical and empirical evidence highlighted in Section 2. In the absence of any literature discussing the lack of influence from equity markets to Bitcoin, this paper suggests that Bitcoin's unique market structure may explain this asymmetric relationship found in this paper. Cryptocurrency markets operate through decentralised, 24/7 global exchanges and instantly respond to speculative global news. This enables Bitcoin to price in information before traditional markets, as there are no restrictions pertaining to regulation or trading hours. Additionally, as Bitcoin is dominated by retail-driven sentiment, and has limited anchoring to macroeconomic fundamentals (Baur et al., 2018), it may be isolated from the effects of short-term movements in equity markets.

These findings differ from previous studies such as Wang et al. (2020) who found a unidirectional relationship from the S&P 500 to Bitcoin and Ahmed et al. (2023) who established bidirectional causality between the two assets. These discrepancies can be attributed to two key factors. Firstly, this paper focuses on a more recent, post-2017 dataset, in contrast from previous literature, capturing a more matured, relevant, and financialized phase of Bitcoin. Secondly, this paper constructed a more robust VAR framework with four control variables; VIX, Gold Returns, Dollar Index and 10-Year Treasury Yield. Previous literature used no or minimal control variables, which may have led to omitted variable bias and contributed to their findings of unidirectionality (Wang et al., 2020) and bidirectionality (Ahmed et al., 2023) between the S&P 500 and Bitcoin. In these cases, the observed impact of the S&P 500 on Bitcoin may have been driven by unaccounted external variables rather than a true causal relationship between the assets. The implementation of the enhanced set of control variables by this study addresses this issue, potentially explaining the discrepancy in results and lack of relationship found from the S&P 500 to Bitcoin.

Furthermore, the results partially align with Bouri et al. (2020), who found heterogeneous behaviour in terms of how Bitcoin interacted with the S&P 500's sectoral indices. Specifically, for the Energy and Financial sector, this paper notes that though the magnitudes of impact were slightly different, the overall impact of Bitcoin's returns on the sectoral indices was similar. This is likely due to both sectors being heavily integrated and influenced by Bitcoin, thus displaying similar dynamics.

Overall, these findings contribute to the growing literature on Bitcoin's relationship with the S&P 500, suggesting that it may function as a leading indicator of market sentiment rather than a reactive asset. Additionally, the evidence suggests that Bitcoin is immune to spillover effects from the S&P 500, likely due to its structural characteristics and isolation from traditional macroeconomic anchors.

5 Conclusion

5.1 Summary

This paper set out to explore the bidirectional relationship between Bitcoin and the S&P 500, both at an aggregate index-level and across two key sectors: Financials and Energy, using daily data from December 2017 to December 2024. The time series econometric analysis consisting of VAR, Granger causality tests, and IRFs revealed a consistent short-run, unidirectional impact from Bitcoin to the S&P 500 and its studied sectors, with no significant reverse effect. These results suggest that Bitcoin has evolved into a financialized and sentiment-sensitive asset, capable of influencing traditional equity markets, especially in sectors with strong links to Bitcoin.

This study contributes to the literature by applying a bidirectional framework and extending the analysis to the Financial and Energy sectors. It also incorporates a broader set of macro-financial control variables to reduce omitted variable bias and includes dummy variables to account for structural breaks. Furthermore, a more recent post-financialisation dataset was used, capturing more relevant Bitcoin price dynamics.

5.2 Limitations and Future Developments

Despite its contributions, this paper acknowledges several limitations that point to opportunities for future research. Firstly, this study only used data from December 2017 onwards. While this captures the post-financialisation phase of Bitcoin, it may have excluded earlier dynamics between the two assets. Future research could use a larger dataset, including data from Bitcoin's inception to offer a broader, more comprehensive understanding of the causal impact between Bitcoin and the S&P 500, potentially highlighting relationships that were not found in this study.

Secondly, the scope of sectoral analysis is restricted to the Financial and Energy sectors due to word count restrictions and to avoid diluting this paper's focus. Though these sectors were chosen based on their theoretical and structural links to Bitcoin, expanding the analysis to all 11 sectors of the S&P 500 could have offered a broader and more comprehensive set of conclusions which would provide-per a more holistic understanding of Bitcoin's impact on the S&P 500's sectoral indices. Additionally, future research could include analysis of various other global indices such as the FTSE 100, TOPIX and the NIFTY 50 to understand how Bitcoin returns can impact global markets rather than just the S&P 500.

Thirdly, as standard VAR models assume constant variance and linear relationships, this study includes dummy variables to account for structural breaks caused by COVID-19 and the FTX collapse. However, to fully capture time-varying volatility and regime-dependent dynamics, future research could employ more flexible, non-linear

frameworks such as Threshold VAR and Markov-switching VAR models, as these may uncover relationships not observed in this study.

Finally, the paper provides strong evidence for a unidirectional relationship from Bitcoin to the S&P 500 and the studied sectors, with no significant reverse causality. This differs from the literature outlined in Section 2; however, this paper argues that the absence of a relationship is attributed to the more robust model specification employed. Nevertheless, the reason for the lack of a relationship from the S&P 500 to Bitcoin cannot be definitively concluded. Future research should further investigate this unexplained asymmetrical relationship to determine if the lack of influence from the S&P 500 to Bitcoin is consistent across different time periods and market conditions, reflecting a genuine market dynamic, or if it is caused by unobserved factors not accounted for in this study.

5.3 Final Remarks

Together, the results provide index-level and sector-specific evidence that post-2017, Bitcoin has evolved to a highly financialised asset with unidirectional short-run influence over the S&P 500 and its Financial and Energy sectors. The empirical analysis supports three of the six alternative hypotheses in Section 3.1, confirming Bitcoin's causal impact on the S&P 500 and studied sectors, while failing to reject the null hypotheses regarding reverse causality. This paper therefore provides updated insights into Bitcoin's evolving market role, suggesting it functions as a leading indicator of the S&P 500's market sentiment rather than a reactive asset. This effect is particularly pronounced in sectors structurally exposed to cryptocurrency dynamics like Financials and Energy. These findings reinforce the interpretation that Bitcoin acts independently, while traditional markets and sectors may be more responsive to cryptocurrency dynamics in the short run.

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7 Appendices

Appendix A: Probability Density Function: Bitcoin Returns Distribution

Source: (Nzokem and Maposa, 2024)

Appendix B: Variable Descriptions

Variable	Description	Frequency	Source
<i>SP500_RET</i>	Log returns of S&P 500 Index	Daily	Bloomberg Terminal
<i>BTC_RET</i>	Log returns of Bitcoin	Daily	CoinGecko Terminal
<i>SPSector_RET</i>	Log returns of S&P Financial and Energy Sectors	Daily	Bloomberg Terminal
<i>VIX</i>	CBOE Volatility Index	Daily	Bloomberg Terminal
<i>GOLD_RET</i>	Log returns of gold prices	Daily	Bloomberg Terminal
<i>DXY</i>	US Dollar Index	Daily	Federal Reserve Economic Data (FRED)
<i>DGS10</i>	10-year US Treasury yield	Daily	US Treasury via FRED (2024)

Appendix C: Eigenvalue stability

	Model I	Model II	
	(BTC and S&P 500) Eigenvalue	(BTC and S&P 500 Financial Sector) Eigenvalue	(BTC and S&P 500 Energy Sector) Eigenvalue
	0.966073	-0.9645743	0.9630586
	-0.966073	0.9645743	-0.9630586
	-0.3469059	.3536822 + .0124215i	0.344091
	0.3469059	.3536822 - .0124215i	-0.344091
	0.3117102	-.3536822 + .0124215i	0.283359
	-0.3117102	-.3536822 - .0124215i	-0.283359
	3.136e-17 + .1722481i	2.773e-16 + .1484156i	2.843e-18 + .1398845i
	3.136e-17 - .1722481i	2.773e-16 - .1484156i	2.843e-18 - .1398845i
	.110448 + .05336099i	.09902859 + .07597519i	.09351588 + .09907601i
	.110448 - .05336099i	.09902859 - .07597519i	.09351588 - .09907601i
	-.110448 + .05336099i	-.09902859 + .07597519i	-.09351588 + .09907601i
	-.110448 - .05336099i	-.09902859 - .07597519i	-.09351588 - .09907601i

7.1 Appendix D: Lagrange-Multiplier Auto residual correlation test

Model 1				
	Lag	Chi2	df	Prob>chi2
(BTC and S&P 500)	1	2.70E+03	36	0.00000
	2	67.3433	36	0.00118
Model II				
	Lag	Chi2	df	Prob>chi2
(BTC and S&P 500 Financial Sector)	1	2.30E+03	36	0
	2	72.7415	36	0.00028
(BTC and S&P 500 Energy Sector)	1	1.90E+03	36	0
	2	67.8662	36	0.00103

Appendix E- Vector Auto Regression

Appendix E1: Vector Auto Regression (Bitcoin and the S&P 500)

	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
BTCReturn						
BTCReturn						
L2.	.0344926	.0246079	1.40	0.161	-.013738	.0827232
SP500Return						
L2.	.0281745	.0883972	0.32	0.750	-.1450807	.2014298
SPVIX						
L2.	.0036314	.0154374	0.24	0.814	-.0266254	.0338883
GoldReturn						
L2.	.0587964	.1156354	0.51	0.611	-.1678449	.2854376
DXY						
L2.	.0001094	.0000836	1.31	0.191	-.0000546	.0002733
D_DGS10						
L2.	-.3495651	.3130815	-1.12	0.264	-.9631936	.2640634
covid_period	.0032183	.0028223	1.14	0.254	-.0023133	.00875
ftx_crash	.0008139	.0053628	0.15	0.879	-.0096969	.0113248
_cons	-.0130412	.009834	-1.33	0.185	-.0323154	.0062331
SP500Return						
BTCReturn						
L2.	.0174645	.0069237	2.52	0.012	.0038944	.0310346
SP500Return						
L2.	.0797206	.0248713	3.21	0.001	.0309737	.1284675
SPVIX						
L2.	.0011912	.0043435	0.27	0.784	-.0073218	.0097043
GoldReturn						
L2.	.0583495	.032535	1.79	0.073	-.005418	.122117
DXY						
L2.	6.11e-06	.0000235	0.26	0.795	-.00004	.0000522
D_DGS10						
L2.	.034761	.0880882	0.39	0.693	-.1378888	.2074107
covid_period	.000198	.0007941	0.25	0.803	-.0013584	.0017544
ftx_crash	.0004513	.0015089	0.30	0.765	-.0025061	.0034086
_cons	-.0006345	.0027669	-0.23	0.819	-.0060575	.0047885

SPVIX						
BTCReturn						
L2.	-.0346656	.0144613	-2.40	0.017	-.0630092	-.0063219
SP500Return						
L2.	.2422327	.0519482	4.66	0.000	.140416	.3440494
SPVIX						
L2.	.9341331	.0090721	102.97	0.000	.9163521	.9519141
GoldReturn						
L2.	-.0297915	.0679553	-0.44	0.661	-.1629815	.1033984
DXY						
L2.	-.0000377	.0000492	-0.77	0.443	-.000134	.0000586
D_DGS10						
L2.	.0245778	.1839882	0.13	0.894	-.3360323	.385188
covid_period	.0055499	.0016586	3.35	0.001	.0022992	.0088007
ftx_crash	-.0000103	.0031515	-0.00	0.997	-.0061872	.0061666
_cons	.0161311	.0057791	2.79	0.005	.0048043	.027458
GoldReturn						
BTCReturn						
L2.	.0000529	.0050461	0.01	0.992	-.0098372	.0099431
SP500Return						
L2.	.0232051	.0181267	1.28	0.200	-.0123227	.0587328
SPVIX						
L2.	.0027411	.0031656	0.87	0.387	-.0034634	.0089456
GoldReturn						
L2.	-.0333113	.0237122	-1.40	0.160	-.0797864	.0131637
DXY						
L2.	-.0000311	.0000172	-1.81	0.070	-.0000647	2.56e-06
D_DGS10						
L2.	.0315472	.0642005	0.49	0.623	-.0942835	.1573779
covid_period	-.000396	.0005787	-0.68	0.494	-.0015303	.0007383
ftx_crash	.0013818	.0010997	1.26	0.209	-.0007736	.0035372
_cons	.00355	.0020166	1.76	0.078	-.0004024	.0075024

DXY						
BTCReturn						
L2.	13.1895	7.785454	1.69	0.090	-2.069705	28.44871
SP500Return						
L2.	6.532003	27.96711	0.23	0.815	-48.28253	61.34653
SPVIX						
L2.	20.95518	4.884101	4.29	0.000	11.38251	30.52784
GoldReturn						
L2.	71.53326	36.58476	1.96	0.051	-.1715529	143.2381
DXY						
L2.	.1260642	.0264633	4.76	0.000	.0741971	.1779313
D_DGS10						
L2.	-216.7855	99.05279	-2.19	0.029	-410.9254	-22.64557
covid_period	-3.942977	.8929228	-4.42	0.000	-5.693074	-2.192881
ftx_crash	2.449118	1.696681	1.44	0.149	-.8763147	5.774551
_cons	98.1355	3.111277	31.54	0.000	92.03751	104.2335
D_DGS10						
BTCReturn						
L2.	.0034367	.0020947	1.64	0.101	-.0006688	.0075421
SP500Return						
L2.	.0065669	.0075245	0.87	0.383	-.0081808	.0213146
SPVIX						
L2.	.0002244	.0013141	0.17	0.864	-.0023511	.0027999
GoldReturn						
L2.	.0052511	.009843	0.53	0.594	-.0140409	.0245431
DXY						
L2.	1.40e-06	7.12e-06	0.20	0.844	-.0000126	.0000154
D_DGS10						
L2.	-.0012619	.0266499	-0.05	0.962	-.0534947	.050971
covid_period	-.0000564	.0002402	-0.23	0.814	-.0005273	.0004144
ftx_crash	-.0001195	.0004565	-0.26	0.794	-.0010142	.0007752
_cons	-.0001876	.0008371	-0.22	0.823	-.0018283	.001453

Appendix E2: Vector Auto Regression (Bitcoin and S&P Financial Sector)

	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
BTCReturn						
BTCReturn L2.	.0345759	.0243769	1.42	0.156	-.0132019	.0823537
SPFinReturn						
SPFinReturn L2.	.0251254	.0705709	0.36	0.722	-.113191	.1634418
SPVIX						
SPVIX L2.	.0036946	.0154136	0.24	0.811	-.0265155	.0339047
GoldReturn						
GoldReturn L2.	.0629991	.1155062	0.55	0.585	-.163389	.2893871
DXY						
DXY L2.	.0001093	.0000836	1.31	0.191	-.0000546	.0002732
D_DGS10						
D_DGS10 L2.	-.3508371	.3131447	-1.12	0.263	-.9645895	.2629153
covid_period	.0032177	.0028201	1.14	0.254	-.0023096	.0087449
ftx_crash	.0007953	.005364	0.15	0.882	-.009718	.0113086
_cons	-.0130438	.0098317	-1.33	0.185	-.0323135	.0062259
SPFinReturn						
BTCReturn L2.	.0230268	.0084311	2.73	0.006	.0065021	.0395516
SPFinReturn						
SPFinReturn L2.	.1056606	.0244081	4.33	0.000	.0578215	.1534996
SPVIX						
SPVIX L2.	-.0002046	.0053311	-0.04	0.969	-.0106533	.0102441
GoldReturn						
GoldReturn L2.	.0821634	.0399498	2.06	0.040	.0038633	.1604635
DXY						
DXY L2.	-5.21e-06	.0000289	-0.18	0.857	-.0000619	.0000515
D_DGS10						
D_DGS10 L2.	.1199826	.1083064	1.11	0.268	-.092294	.3322592
covid_period	.0001803	.0009754	0.18	0.853	-.0017314	.002092
ftx_crash	.0010876	.0018552	0.59	0.558	-.0025486	.0047238
_cons	.0008093	.0034004	0.24	0.812	-.0058554	.0074741

SPVIX						
BTCReturn						
L2.	-.0275969	.0143686	-1.92	0.055	-.055759	.0005651
SPFinReturn						
L2.	.1368115	.0415972	3.29	0.001	.0552825	.2183404
SPVIX						
L2.	.9315453	.0090854	102.53	0.000	.9137383	.9493523
GoldReturn						
L2.	.000601	.0680838	0.01	0.993	-.1328407	.1340428
DXY						
L2.	-.0000377	.0000493	-0.77	0.444	-.0001344	.0000589
D_DGS10						
L2.	.0229441	.1845794	0.12	0.901	-.3388249	.384713
covid_period	.0058059	.0016623	3.49	0.000	.0025479	.0090639
ftx_crash	.0000854	.0031618	0.03	0.978	-.0061116	.0062823
_cons	.0166252	.0057952	2.87	0.004	.0052669	.0279835
GoldReturn						
BTCReturn						
L2.	.0004263	.0049991	0.09	0.932	-.0093719	.0102244
SPFinReturn						
L2.	.0168942	.0144725	1.17	0.243	-.0114713	.0452597
SPVIX						
L2.	.0026429	.003161	0.84	0.403	-.0035525	.0088383
GoldReturn						
L2.	-.0301253	.0236877	-1.27	0.203	-.0765523	.0163017
DXY						
L2.	-.0000311	.0000172	-1.81	0.070	-.0000647	2.54e-06
D_DGS10						
L2.	.0309458	.0642188	0.48	0.630	-.0949208	.1568124
covid_period	-.000384	.0005783	-0.66	0.507	-.0015175	.0007495
ftx_crash	.0013787	.0011	1.25	0.210	-.0007773	.0035348
_cons	.0035726	.0020163	1.77	0.076	-.0003791	.0075244

DXY						
BTCReturn						
L2.	14.79371	7.711692	1.92	0.055	-.3209299	29.90835
SPFinReturn						
L2.	-13.9356	22.32531	-0.62	0.532	-57.69241	29.82121
SPVIX						
L2.	20.18871	4.876141	4.14	0.000	10.63165	29.74577
GoldReturn						
L2.	71.07545	36.54074	1.95	0.052	-.5430906	142.694
DXY						
L2.	.1261692	.026461	4.77	0.000	.0743066	.1780318
D_DGS10						
L2.	-214.7595	99.06428	-2.17	0.030	-408.922	-20.5971
covid_period	-3.877828	.8921463	-4.35	0.000	-5.626402	-2.129253
ftx_crash	2.508673	1.696922	1.48	0.139	-.8172319	5.834578
_cons	98.26375	3.110279	31.59	0.000	92.16771	104.3598
D_DGS10						
BTCReturn						
L2.	.0034913	.002075	1.68	0.092	-.0005756	.0075582
SPFinReturn						
L2.	.0054173	.006007	0.90	0.367	-.0063562	.0171909
SPVIX						
L2.	.0002218	.001312	0.17	0.866	-.0023497	.0027933
GoldReturn						
L2.	.0061989	.009832	0.63	0.528	-.0130714	.0254692
DXY						
L2.	1.39e-06	7.12e-06	0.20	0.845	-.0000126	.0000153
D_DGS10						
L2.	-.0015068	.0266551	-0.06	0.955	-.0537498	.0507362
covid_period	-.0000551	.00024	-0.23	0.818	-.0005256	.0004154
ftx_crash	-.0001224	.0004566	-0.27	0.789	-.0010173	.0007725
_cons	-.0001854	.0008369	-0.22	0.825	-.0018256	.0014549

Appendix E3: Vector Auto Regression (Bitcoin and Energy)

	Coefficient	Std. err.	z	P> z	[95% conf. interval]	
BTCReturn						
BTCReturn L2.	.0355833	.0240317	1.48	0.139	-.011518	.0826846
SPEnergyReturn						
SPEnergyReturn L2.	.0131639	.05111	0.26	0.797	-.0870099	.1133376
SPVIX L2.	.003134	.0152521	0.21	0.837	-.0267595	.0330275
GoldReturn L2.	.0592931	.1156267	0.51	0.608	-.1673311	.2859173
DXY L2.	.0001096	.0000836	1.31	0.190	-.0000544	.0002735
D_DGS10 L2.	-.3490327	.3130719	-1.11	0.265	-.9626424	.2645769
covid_period	.0032773	.0028119	1.17	0.244	-.002234	.0087887
ftx_crash	.0008682	.0053593	0.16	0.871	-.0096359	.0113723
_cons	-.0129749	.009828	-1.32	0.187	-.0322374	.0062876
SPEnergyReturn						
BTCReturn L2.	.0377281	.0112781	3.35	0.001	.0156233	.0598328
SPEnergyReturn						
SPEnergyReturn L2.	.0488885	.0239861	2.04	0.042	.0018766	.0959003
SPVIX L2.	.0059975	.0071578	0.84	0.402	-.0080316	.0200266
GoldReturn L2.	.0411476	.0542639	0.76	0.448	-.0652077	.147503
DXY L2.	-.0000285	.0000393	-0.73	0.468	-.0001054	.0000485
D_DGS10 L2.	.1643806	.1469255	1.12	0.263	-.123588	.4523492
covid_period	-.0011715	.0013197	-0.89	0.375	-.003758	.001415
ftx_crash	-.0003815	.0025152	-0.15	0.879	-.0053111	.0045481
_cons	.0024749	.0046123	0.54	0.592	-.006565	.0115149

SPVIX						
BTCReturn						
L2.	-.0213612	.0141908	-1.51	0.132	-.0491747	.0064523
SPEnergyReturn						
L2.	.0618786	.0301807	2.05	0.040	.0027255	.1210317
SPVIX						
L2.	.9281707	.0090064	103.06	0.000	.9105184	.945823
GoldReturn						
L2.	-.0181751	.0682781	-0.27	0.790	-.1519977	.1156475
DXY						
L2.	-.0000363	.0000494	-0.73	0.462	-.0001331	.0000605
D_DGS10						
L2.	.0336226	.1848704	0.18	0.856	-.3287167	.3959619
covid_period	.0061483	.0016605	3.70	0.000	.0028938	.0094027
ftx_crash	.0004887	.0031647	0.15	0.877	-.005714	.0066914
_cons	.0170709	.0058035	2.94	0.003	.0056963	.0284455
GoldReturn						
BTCReturn						
L2.	.0008202	.0049282	0.17	0.868	-.0088388	.0104792
SPEnergyReturn						
L2.	.0125538	.0104811	1.20	0.231	-.0079888	.0330964
SPVIX						
L2.	.0023876	.0031277	0.76	0.445	-.0037426	.0085179
GoldReturn						
L2.	-.0331473	.0237115	-1.40	0.162	-.0796211	.0133264
DXY						
L2.	-.0000309	.0000172	-1.80	0.072	-.0000645	2.76e-06
D_DGS10						
L2.	.0318365	.0642016	0.50	0.620	-.0939962	.1576693
covid_period	-.0003505	.0005766	-0.61	0.543	-.0014807	.0007797
ftx_crash	.0014254	.001099	1.30	0.195	-.0007286	.0035795
_cons	.0035922	.0020154	1.78	0.075	-.0003579	.0075424

DXY							
BTCReturn							
L2.	15.25241	7.599779	2.01	0.045	.3571155	30.1477	
SPEnergyReturn							
L2.	-20.59153	16.16301	-1.27	0.203	-52.27046	11.0874	
SPVIX							
L2.	20.06293	4.823314	4.16	0.000	10.60941	29.51645	
GoldReturn							
L2.	75.03402	36.56576	2.05	0.040	3.36645	146.7016	
DXY							
L2.	.1258833	.0264521	4.76	0.000	.0740382	.1777285	
D_DGS10							
L2.	-214.6027	99.00578	-2.17	0.030	-408.6505	-20.55496	
covid_period	-3.887358	.8892488	-4.37	0.000	-5.630254	-2.144462	
ftx_crash	2.476582	1.694838	1.46	0.144	-.8452387	5.798403	
_cons	98.32143	3.107997	31.63	0.000	92.22987	104.413	
D_DGS10							
BTCReturn							
L2.	.0038866	.002046	1.90	0.057	-.0001235	.0078967	
SPEnergyReturn							
L2.	.0005117	.0043514	0.12	0.906	-.0080169	.0090403	
SPVIX							
L2.	.0000245	.0012985	0.02	0.985	-.0025206	.0025696	
GoldReturn							
L2.	.005733	.0098442	0.58	0.560	-.0135614	.0250273	
DXY							
L2.	1.43e-06	7.12e-06	0.20	0.841	-.0000125	.0000154	
D_DGS10							
L2.	-.0009151	.0266543	-0.03	0.973	-.0531567	.0513264	
covid_period	-.0000381	.0002394	-0.16	0.873	-.0005074	.0004311	
ftx_crash	-.0001052	.0004563	-0.23	0.818	-.0009995	.0007891	
_cons	-.0001537	.0008367	-0.18	0.854	-.0017937	.0014862	

Appendix F - Granger Causality Test

Appendix F1: Granger Causality Test (Bitcoin and the S&P 500)

Granger causality Wald tests

Equation	Excluded	chi2	df	Prob > chi2
BTCReturn	SP500Return	.10159	1	0.750
BTCReturn	SPVIX	.05534	1	0.814
BTCReturn	GoldReturn	.25853	1	0.611
BTCReturn	DXY	1.7095	1	0.191
BTCReturn	D_DGS10	1.2466	1	0.264
BTCReturn	ALL	2.619	5	0.758
SP500Return	BTCReturn	6.3627	1	0.012
SP500Return	SPVIX	.07522	1	0.784
SP500Return	GoldReturn	3.2164	1	0.073
SP500Return	DXY	.06731	1	0.795
SP500Return	D_DGS10	.15572	1	0.693
SP500Return	ALL	10.783	5	0.056
SPVIX	BTCReturn	5.7462	1	0.017
SPVIX	SP500Return	21.743	1	0.000
SPVIX	GoldReturn	.19219	1	0.661
SPVIX	DXY	.58815	1	0.443
SPVIX	D_DGS10	.01784	1	0.894
SPVIX	ALL	23.842	5	0.000
GoldReturn	BTCReturn	.00011	1	0.992
GoldReturn	SP500Return	1.6388	1	0.200
GoldReturn	SPVIX	.74978	1	0.387
GoldReturn	DXY	3.2792	1	0.070
GoldReturn	D_DGS10	.24146	1	0.623
GoldReturn	ALL	5.3171	5	0.378
DXY	BTCReturn	2.87	1	0.090
DXY	SP500Return	.05455	1	0.815
DXY	SPVIX	18.408	1	0.000
DXY	GoldReturn	3.8231	1	0.051
DXY	D_DGS10	4.7899	1	0.029
DXY	ALL	32.01	5	0.000
D_DGS10	BTCReturn	2.6919	1	0.101
D_DGS10	SP500Return	.76167	1	0.383
D_DGS10	SPVIX	.02917	1	0.864
D_DGS10	GoldReturn	.28461	1	0.594
D_DGS10	DXY	.03866	1	0.844
D_DGS10	ALL	5.2679	5	0.384

Appendix F2: Granger Causality Test (Bitcoin and the S&P Financial Sector)

Granger causality Wald tests

Equation	Excluded	chi2	df	Prob > chi2
BTCReturn	SPFinReturn	.12676	1	0.722
BTCReturn	SPVIX	.05746	1	0.811
BTCReturn	GoldReturn	.29748	1	0.585
BTCReturn	DXY	1.7077	1	0.191
BTCReturn	D_DGS10	1.2552	1	0.263
BTCReturn	ALL	2.6443	5	0.755
SPFinReturn	BTCReturn	7.4593	1	0.006
SPFinReturn	SPVIX	.00147	1	0.969
SPFinReturn	GoldReturn	4.2299	1	0.040
SPFinReturn	DXY	.03239	1	0.857
SPFinReturn	D_DGS10	1.2272	1	0.268
SPFinReturn	ALL	14.134	5	0.015
SPVIX	BTCReturn	3.6888	1	0.055
SPVIX	SPFinReturn	10.817	1	0.001
SPVIX	GoldReturn	7.8e-05	1	0.993
SPVIX	DXY	.58543	1	0.444
SPVIX	D_DGS10	.01545	1	0.901
SPVIX	ALL	12.903	5	0.024
GoldReturn	BTCReturn	.00727	1	0.932
GoldReturn	SPFinReturn	1.3627	1	0.243
GoldReturn	SPVIX	.69908	1	0.403
GoldReturn	DXY	3.2839	1	0.070
GoldReturn	D_DGS10	.23221	1	0.630
GoldReturn	ALL	5.0404	5	0.411
DXY	BTCReturn	3.6801	1	0.055
DXY	SPFinReturn	.38963	1	0.532
DXY	SPVIX	17.142	1	0.000
DXY	GoldReturn	3.7834	1	0.052
DXY	D_DGS10	4.6997	1	0.030
DXY	ALL	32.351	5	0.000
D_DGS10	BTCReturn	2.831	1	0.092
D_DGS10	SPFinReturn	.8133	1	0.367
D_DGS10	SPVIX	.02858	1	0.866
D_DGS10	GoldReturn	.39751	1	0.528
D_DGS10	DXY	.03806	1	0.845
D_DGS10	ALL	5.3197	5	0.378

Appendix F3: Granger Causality Test (Bitcoin and Energy)

Granger causality Wald tests

Equation	Excluded	chi2	df	Prob > chi2
BTCReturn	SPEnergyReturn	.06634	1	0.797
BTCReturn	SPVIX	.04222	1	0.837
BTCReturn	GoldReturn	.26296	1	0.608
BTCReturn	DXY	1.7164	1	0.190
BTCReturn	D_DGS10	1.2429	1	0.265
BTCReturn	ALL	2.5837	5	0.764
SPEnergyReturn	BTCReturn	11.191	1	0.001
SPEnergyReturn	SPVIX	.70206	1	0.402
SPEnergyReturn	GoldReturn	.575	1	0.448
SPEnergyReturn	DXY	.52607	1	0.468
SPEnergyReturn	D_DGS10	1.2517	1	0.263
SPEnergyReturn	ALL	13.612	5	0.018
SPVIX	BTCReturn	2.2659	1	0.132
SPVIX	SPEnergyReturn	4.2036	1	0.040
SPVIX	GoldReturn	.07086	1	0.790
SPVIX	DXY	.53996	1	0.462
SPVIX	D_DGS10	.03308	1	0.856
SPVIX	ALL	6.2822	5	0.280
GoldReturn	BTCReturn	.0277	1	0.868
GoldReturn	SPEnergyReturn	1.4346	1	0.231
GoldReturn	SPVIX	.58275	1	0.445
GoldReturn	DXY	3.2367	1	0.072
GoldReturn	D_DGS10	.2459	1	0.620
GoldReturn	ALL	5.1125	5	0.402
DXY	BTCReturn	4.0279	1	0.045
DXY	SPEnergyReturn	1.6231	1	0.203
DXY	SPVIX	17.302	1	0.000
DXY	GoldReturn	4.2108	1	0.040
DXY	D_DGS10	4.6984	1	0.030
DXY	ALL	33.607	5	0.000
D_DGS10	BTCReturn	3.6085	1	0.057
D_DGS10	SPEnergyReturn	.01383	1	0.906
D_DGS10	SPVIX	.00036	1	0.985
D_DGS10	GoldReturn	.33916	1	0.560
D_DGS10	DXY	.04013	1	0.841
D_DGS10	ALL	4.5182	5	0.477

Appendix G - Impulse response functions

G1: Appendix G1 - Impulse Response Function (Effect of Bitcoin Shock on S&P 500)

Graphs by irfname, impulse variable, and response variable

Appendix G2 - S & P Shock Impact on Bitcoin

Graphs by irfname, impulse variable, and response variable

Appendix G3 - S & P Shock Impact on S & P Financial sector

Graphs by irfname, impulse variable, and response variable

Appendix G4 - S & P Shock Impact on S & P Energy Sector

Graphs by irfname, impulse variable, and response variable

Appendix G5 – S & P Financial Sector Shock Impact on Bitcoin

Graphs by irfname, impulse variable, and response variable

Appendix G6 - S & P Energy Sector Shock Impact on Bitcoin

Graphs by irfname, impulse variable, and response variable